

Dynamically Fine-Tuned Neural Compressor For FDD Massive MIMO CSI Feedback

Mehdi Sattari

dept. Electrical Engineering
Chalmers University of Technology
Gothenburg, Sweden
mehdi.sattari@chalmers.se

Deniz Gündüz

dept. Electrical and Electronic Engineering
Imperial College London
London, UK
d.gunduz@imperial.ac.uk

Tommy Svensson

dept. Electrical Engineering
Chalmers University of Technology
Gothenburg, Sweden
tommy.svensson@chalmers.se

Abstract—Efficient channel state information (CSI) compression is essential in frequency division duplexing (FDD) massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems to mitigate excessive feedback overhead. While deep learning-based methods achieve superior performance, they struggle with distribution shifts, leading to degradation in their performance. To address this, we propose a model fine-tuning approach for CSI feedback, dynamically updating encoder/decoder networks using recent CSI samples. We adopt a full-model fine-tuning scheme, jointly updating the encoder and decoder model while accounting for the additional feedback overhead imposed by conveying the updated decoder parameters. Our results demonstrate that full-model fine-tuning significantly enhances the rate-distortion (RD) performance of neural CSI compression. Furthermore, we analyze how often the full-model fine-tuning should be applied in a new wireless environment and identify an optimal period interval for achieving the best RD trade-off.

Index Terms—CSI compression, massive MIMO, deep learning, fine-tuning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) is a key technology for 5G and beyond, enabling high-resolution beamforming with massive antenna arrays at the base station (BS) to serve multiple users simultaneously, thereby boosting spectral efficiency. For frequency division duplexing (FDD) massive MIMO systems, channel state information (CSI) compression is essential to reduce feedback overhead. Various techniques, such as compressed sensing [1], vector quantization [2], and deep learning [3]–[7], have been explored. However, compressed sensing approaches struggle with finding an optimal basis for CSI projection and are computationally expensive, making them impractical for massive MIMO [1]. Meanwhile, in vector quantization, overhead scales linearly with channel

dimensions, limiting scalability for large systems [2]. In contrast, recent advancements in data-driven compression, enabled by progress in deep neural network (DNN) architectures, have demonstrated significant gains across various data modalities, including CSI [3]–[7].

Machine learning models often perform well on test sets with distributions similar to their training data but can fail in deployment when distributions shift. This issue is common in wireless networks, where channel statistics vary due to mobility, environmental changes, or interference [8]. Some studies have addressed distribution shifts in CSI compression [9]–[11]. In [9], deep transfer learning mitigates distribution shifts while reducing training costs, and a meta-learning algorithm minimizes required CSI samples. In [10], a lightweight translation model and domain-based data augmentation are introduced. Specifically, a “CSI-TransNet” module is proposed for scenario-adaptive feedback and “SPTM2-ISTANet” for efficient CSI compression. A single-encoder-to-multiple-decoders (S-to-M) approach is presented in [11], using multi-task learning to unify independent autoencoders into a shared-encoder framework with task-specific decoders.

These prior works tackling the distribution shift problem in CSI compression have primarily concentrated on vanilla autoencoder-based CSI compression, neglecting bit-level CSI compression [9]–[11]. However, in practice, quantization and entropy encoding/decoding must be employed to effectively encode the low-dimensional latent space. Additionally, existing solutions either ignore the overhead required to feedback model updates to the decoder side [9], [10], leave the pre-trained neural CSI compressor unchanged during fine-tuning [10], or impose restrictive conditions such as requiring the same encoder for different channel scenarios and limiting the fine-tuning to a finite number of models [11].

To address the problem of distribution shift in neural CSI compression, we explore a different approach by fine-tuning the encoder and decoder models in an end-to-end fashion using a small number of recent measurements. Since the encoder (i.e., the user) has access to the CSI matrices to be compressed, it can track the data statistics, and continuously adapt the encoder and decoder parameters through gradual fine-tuning. The challenge here is that the updates to the decoder side would need to be communicated over the feedback link,

This work has been supported in part by the project SEMANTIC, funded by the EU’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 861165, and in part by the Hexa-X-II project which has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101095759. D. Gündüz received funding from the UKRI through ERC consolidator project AI-R under grant EP/X030806/1, and from the Horizon Europe SNS project ‘6G-GOALS’ under grant 101139232. The computations were enabled by resources provided by the National Academic Infrastructure for Supercomputing in Sweden (NAISS), partially funded by the Swedish Research Council through grant agreement no. 2022-06725.

Fig. 1. The neural CSI compressor architecture.

which introduces additional overhead. Our goal is to develop a neural CSI fine-tuning algorithm that optimizes latent rate and distortion loss while accounting for the feedback overhead needed for model updates. Furthermore, we analyze how often fine-tuning should be applied to update the models. The less frequent the model updates are, the smaller the bit rate cost for model updates is, but the higher the compression rate to achieve the same CSI distortion becomes due to the mismatch between training and test statistics. On the other hand, while a higher model update frequency would make CSI compression more efficient, this comes at the expense of increased bit rate cost for model updates. Our analysis identifies an optimal update frequency resulting in the best rate-distortion (RD) trade-off.

II. BACKBONE NEURAL CSI COMPRESSOR

We consider FDD transmission, where a massive MIMO BS serves several single-antenna users. The BS is equipped with a uniform linear array (ULA) of N_t antennas. Orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) is used for downlink transmission across N_c subcarriers. The downlink CSI matrix in the spatial-frequency domain is denoted by:

$$\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{h}_1, \dots, \mathbf{h}_{N_c}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_t \times N_c}. \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1 illustrates the architecture of our backbone neural CSI compressor, where the input consists of the real and imaginary parts of the spatial-frequency channel matrix. Encoder function f_ϕ uses convolutional layers with activation functions to transform the high-dimensional massive MIMO channel matrix \mathbf{H} into a lower-dimensional latent representation \mathbf{Z} . The first two layers apply 64 convolutional kernels (size 5) with ReLU activation, while the final layer uses 2 kernels with a linear activation function. Max pooling (pool size 2) is applied in the first and second layers to reduce the input dimension.

After acquiring the low-dimensional latent space, quantization Q and entropy coding γ_θ are applied to transform the latent representation into a bit sequence. Specifically, a

uniform scalar quantizer with a unit quantization bin converts continuous latent values into discrete values. Based on the latent probability distribution learned during training, a lossless compression algorithm such as range coding is used to entropy code the quantized latent space, producing a variable-length bit stream. Incorporating quantization into the compressor poses a challenge for training via backpropagation, as the derivative of quantization is zero almost everywhere. To address this, a common approach is to approximate quantization by adding independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) uniform noise, $\Delta \mathbf{Z} \sim U(0, 1)$, to the latent representation, i.e., $\tilde{\mathbf{Z}} = \mathbf{Z} + \Delta \mathbf{Z}$.

On the decoder side, entropy-coded quantized bit stream is decoded first, and the low-dimensional channel matrix is recovered by the decoding network. The entropy encoder and decoder share the same prior distribution for the latent space. In our architecture, we adopt a fully factorized distribution based on a neural network called DeepFactorized [12]. This distribution leverages DNNs to learn and represent latent distribution while assuming certain factorization properties. The decoder neural network, represented by function g_θ in our model (depicted in Fig. 1), consists of convolutional layers with a kernel size of 5 and ReLU activations. To reconstruct the large channel matrix from the entropy-decoded representation, an upsampling factor of 2 is applied in the first and second layers.

To evaluate the performance of our trained neural CSI compressor, we use the DeepMIMO dataset, which generates MIMO channels based on ray-tracing simulations from Remcom Wireless InSite [13]. Specifically, we train the compressor in the static outdoor scenario ‘O1’ at a 3.5 GHz carrier frequency. Table I provides details on the dataset parameters used in our simulations. We generate 29,865 CSI samples, splitting them into 40%, 40%, and 20% for training, validation, and testing, respectively. Training employs the RD loss function defined in (2), optimizing encoder and decoder weights along with the factorized distribution for entropy coding.

$$L_{RD}(\phi, \theta) = \mathbb{E} \left[-\log_2 p_\theta \left(Q(f_\phi(\mathbf{H})) \right) + \lambda \left\| g_\theta \left(Q^{-1} \left(Q(f_\phi(\mathbf{H})) \right) \right) - \mathbf{H} \right\|^2 \right], \quad (2)$$

here, λ acts as a regularizer that governs the trade-off between the rate and distortion terms and p_θ is the prior probability modeling the distribution of the latent space.

The neural CSI compressor is implemented in Python 3.9 using TensorFlow. We use the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 and a batch size of 32, updating network parameters over 200 epochs. We assess the performance of the neural CSI compressor in terms of the RD trade-off achieved, where the distortion is measured as the normalized mean squared error (NMSE), defined as

$$\text{NMSE} \triangleq \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\|\mathbf{H} - \hat{\mathbf{H}}\|^2}{\|\mathbf{H}\|^2} \right], \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{H} and $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ are the true and reconstructed channel matrices, respectively. The bit rate of the entropy-coded latent

TABLE I
DEEPMIMO DATASET PARAMETERS

DeepMIMO parameters	Value
Scenario	O1
Center frequency	3.5 GHz
Number of paths	10
Active users	from row 1100 to 2200
Active BS number	BS 5
Bandwidth	50 MHz
Number of OFDM subcarriers	64
BS antennas	$N_x = 1, N_y = 64, N_z = 1$
UE antennas	$N_x = 1, N_y = 1, N_z = 1$

Fig. 2. RD performance of the backbone neural CSI compressor.

representation is estimated by the entropy of the quantized values:

$$R = \mathbb{E}[-\log_2 p_\theta(Q(\mathbf{Z}))]. \quad (4)$$

The RD curve in Fig. 2 demonstrates the performance of our trained neural CSI compressor for different values of λ , specifically $\lambda = 5 \times 10^4, 10^5, 5 \times 10^5$, and 10^6 . This figure confirms that the trained neural CSI compressor performs well when tested with (unseen) CSI realizations sampled from the same environment.

III. CSI FEEDBACK FINE-TUNING

Fine-tuning a neural CSI compressor involves updating the backbone model parameters, i.e., ϕ_0 and θ_0 for the encoder and decoder networks, respectively, which were trained on a generic dataset. Fine-tuning with new CSI samples results in updated parameters, ϕ and θ , for the encoder and decoder, where only the decoder parameters need to be transmitted in the bitstream from the transmitter to the receiver, resulting in additional communication overhead. To minimize this overhead, we update only the last layer of the decoder network and the latent prior weights. Let these updated model parameters be denoted as $\tilde{\theta}$. We then encode the partial decoder model updates, defined as $\delta \triangleq \tilde{\theta} - \tilde{\theta}_0$, alongside the latent space \mathbf{Z} , where $\tilde{\theta}_0$ represents the backbone neural CSI compressor parameters associated with the last layer of the decoder network and the latent prior weights.

Algorithm 1 Full-model Fine-tuning - Encoding

Input: $\{\theta_0, \phi_0\}$, batch size B , $\mathcal{H} = \{\mathcal{H}_T, \mathcal{H}_E\}$.

Output: Compressed bitstream $b = (b_{\bar{\delta}}, b_z)$.

Initialize model parameters: $\phi = \phi_0$, and $\theta = \theta_0$

for epoch = 1 to num_epochs **do**
for each batch b in \mathcal{H}_T **do**

Load data batch $\mathbf{H} \in \{\mathcal{H}_b\}_{b=1}^B$ from \mathcal{H}_T .

Quantize updated decoder parameters: $\tilde{\theta} = Q_t(\delta) + \theta_0$, with $\delta = \tilde{\theta} - \tilde{\theta}_0$.

Apply feature encoder and quantization, $\mathbf{Z} = f_\phi(\mathbf{H})$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{Z}} = \mathbf{Z} + \Delta\mathbf{Z}$.

Apply feature decoder, $\hat{\mathbf{H}} = g_{\tilde{\theta}}(\tilde{\mathbf{Z}})$.

Compute loss $L_{RD}(\phi, \tilde{\theta})$ according to equation (2).

Update θ, ϕ using gradients $\partial L_{RD}(\phi, \tilde{\theta})/\partial \tilde{\theta}$ and $\partial L_{RD}(\phi, \tilde{\theta})/\partial \phi$.

end for

end for

return Fine-tuned model parameters $\{\phi^*, \theta^*\}$.

Compress $\mathbf{H} \in \mathcal{H}_E$ to latent representation $\bar{\mathbf{Z}} = Q(f_{\phi^*}(\mathbf{H}))$.

Compute quantized model parameters: $\bar{\theta} = \theta_0 + \bar{\delta}$, with $\bar{\delta} = Q_t(\theta^* - \theta_0)$.

Entropy encode: $b_{\bar{\delta}} = \gamma(\bar{\delta}; p[\bar{\delta}])$ and $b_z = \gamma_{\bar{\theta}}(\bar{\mathbf{Z}}; p_{\bar{\theta}})$.

Algorithm 2 Full-model Fine-tuning - Decoding

Input: θ_0 , model prior $p[\bar{\delta}]$, bitstream $b = (b_z, b_{\bar{\delta}})$.

Output: Decompressed CSI matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$.

Entropy decode: $\bar{\delta} = \gamma^{-1}(b_{\bar{\delta}}; p[\bar{\delta}])$

Compute decoder's updated parameters under model prior: $\tilde{\theta} = \theta_0 + \bar{\delta}$.

Entropy decode latent under fine-tuned prior: $\bar{\mathbf{Z}} = \gamma_{\tilde{\theta}}^{-1}(b_z; p_{\tilde{\theta}})$.

Apply de-quantization and feature decoder: $\hat{\mathbf{H}} = Q^{-1}(g_{\tilde{\theta}}(\bar{\mathbf{Z}}))$.

To encode the decoder model update vector, we first quantize it. Unlike the unit bin quantization used for the latent space, we employ a higher-resolution quantizer for model updates. In particular, we use N uniform bins of width t , and define the quantization function for model updates as follows [14]:

$$\bar{\delta} = Q_t(\delta) = \text{clip}\left(\left\lfloor \frac{\delta}{t} \right\rfloor t, -\frac{(N-1)t}{2}, \frac{(N-1)t}{2}\right), \quad (5)$$

where clipping and rounding operations are defined as:

$$\text{clip}(x, x_{\min}, x_{\max}) = \begin{cases} x_{\min}, & \text{if } x < x_{\min}, \\ x, & \text{if } x_{\min} \leq x \leq x_{\max}, \\ x_{\max}, & \text{if } x > x_{\max}, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$\lfloor x \rfloor = \begin{cases} \lfloor x \rfloor, & \text{if } x - \lfloor x \rfloor < 0.5, \\ \lceil x \rceil, & \text{if } x - \lfloor x \rfloor \geq 0.5. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Here, the quantization bin is controlled by t , and N is a hyperparameter that specifies the number of bins. Given that

Fig. 3. Simulation layout of QuaDRiGa dataset [15].

$\bar{\delta} = Q_t(\delta)$, the discrete model prior $p[\bar{\delta}]$ is derived by pushing forward $p(\delta)$ through the quantization function Q_t :

$$\begin{aligned}
 p[\bar{\delta}] &= \int_{Q_t^{-1}(\bar{\delta})} p(\delta) d\delta \\
 &= \int_{\bar{\delta}-t/2}^{\bar{\delta}+t/2} p(\delta) d\delta \\
 &= P(\delta < \bar{\delta} + t/2) - P(\delta < \bar{\delta} - t/2).
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

After quantization, a model prior $p(\delta)$ must be considered to entropy code the discrete model updates. We consider the uniform distribution as defined below:

$$\delta \sim U(-tN, tN). \tag{9}$$

We summarize the encoding and decoding of the full-model fine-tuning in Algorithms 1 and 2, respectively. It is important to emphasize that during fine-tuning and parameter updates, we use CSI samples collected in the new environment, denoted as \mathcal{H}_T . For evaluation, however, the fine-tuned network is applied to CSI samples collected after the fine-tuning period, denoted as \mathcal{H}_E .

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we evaluate the effectiveness of various fine-tuning schemes applied to the backbone model in a new environment with varying channel statistics. We test the fine-tuning approaches in a completely different setting using the QuaDRiGa [15] dataset. In this scenario, a BS equipped with a ULA of 64 antennas and 64 OFDM subcarriers is deployed in an urban environment, positioned on a rooftop. A mobile user moves along a 350-meter linear track at a speed of 5 km/h. The simulation follows the Madrid grid 3D model developed by the METIS project. The layout of this setup is shown in Fig. 3, with the dataset parameters detailed in Table II.

Throughout the plots in this section, we refer to the following fine-tuning schemes. Note that, for a fair comparison, we use our backbone neural CSI compressor trained with the RD loss, rather than the vanilla autoencoders used in previous works.

TABLE II
QUADRIGA DATASET PARAMETERS

parameters	Value
Center frequency	3.7 GHz
Bandwidth	50 MHz
Number of OFDM subcarriers	64
Number of BS Antennas	64
Number of user Antennas	1
User (initial) position	(15, 415, 1.2)
BS position	(267, 267, 60)
BS orientation	$\pi/2$ (facing north)
Sample frequency	27.1521 samples/meter

- **“No FT”** represents the pre-trained neural CSI compressor applied without fine-tuning in the new environment.
- **“EO”** refers to encoder-only fine-tuning, where only the encoder weights are updated while the decoder and latent prior weights remain frozen. No additional feedback is required for model updates.
- **“FM”** denotes full-model fine-tuning, where both the encoder and decoder are fine-tuned. We use $t = 0.0001$, $N = 100$, and train for 1500 epochs.
- **“GA”** (genie-aided fine-tuning) assumes the decoder has perfect knowledge of model updates without additional feedback overhead, serving as a lower bound for fine-tuning performance. The method in [9] aligns with the “GA” scheme, as it fine-tunes a vanilla autoencoder without considering feedback overhead.
- **“TM”** represents the ‘translation module’ from [10]. It adapts input data to a new domain using convolutional translation and retranslation modules at the encoder and decoder, respectively. We adopt the same network architecture and sparsity-aligning function as [10].

We compare the aforementioned fine-tuning schemes in Fig. 4 using the QuaDRiGa dataset, with a learning rate of 0.001 in all simulations. The results indicate that the “EO” and “TM” fine-tuning schemes provide only marginal improvements in RD performance. This suggests that modifying only the encoder or applying domain adaptation techniques is insufficient to fully adapt the model to new CSI statistics. In contrast, the “FM” fine-tuning approach achieves a significant RD performance boost. This finding underscores the importance of end-to-end fine-tuning of the entire model.

For full-model fine-tuning, there is a trade-off in determining how frequently it should be applied in a new environment. To explore this, we apply full-model fine-tuning at varying distances for the mobile user in the QuaDRiGa dataset. The RD plot in Fig. 5, with $\lambda = 5 \times 10^5$, shows that the optimal fine-tuning distance for RD performance is between 8 and 16 meters. More frequent updates (< 8 m) incur high model update costs, while less frequent updates (> 16 m) increase channel variation, degrading RD performance. Thus, operators must balance update frequency to optimize compression efficiency.

Table III compares the number of floating-point operations (FLOPs) required during inference and the number of

Fig. 4. The RD plot for different fine-tuning schemes.

Fig. 5. Full-model RD performance across varying distances for the mobile user in the QuaDRiGa dataset.

trainable parameters for different fine-tuning schemes. The computational cost of fine-tuning depends on the complexity of the backbone neural compressor and the CSI dimensions. As the table shows, our backbone network exhibits moderate complexity compared to many architectures in the literature, requiring approximately 475 FLOPs during inference. For comparison, the authors of [10] employed SPTM2-ISTANet+, which unfolds an iterative shrinkage-thresholding algorithm and requires significantly more computation—approximately 25.5 billion FLOPs for 12 iterations.

V. CONCLUSION

This work introduced a full-model fine-tuning scheme for the neural CSI compressor. We considered a neural CSI compressor that optimizes both distortion and the bit rate required for transmitting the quantized latent vector by minimizing the RD loss function. We proposed a full-model update algorithm that accounts for transmitting model updates to the decoder along with the latent representation. Simulation results demonstrate that full-model fine-tuning is essential for

TABLE III
NUMBER OF FLOPS AND TRAINABLE PARAMETERS FOR DIFFERENT FINE-TUNING SCHEMES M: MILLION, K: THOUSAND.

	Parameters	FLOPs
EO	109 K	475 M
FM	218 K	475 M
TM	8 K	521 M

adapting the neural CSI compressor to a new environment. Additionally, we analyzed the duration for which the full-model fine-tuning scheme can be effectively applied in a new environment, highlighting the trade-offs between the efficiency of more frequent updates and their communication cost.

REFERENCES

- [1] X. Rao and V. K. N. Lau, “Distributed compressive CSIT estimation and feedback for FDD multi-user massive MIMO systems,” *IEEE Trans. Signal Process.*, vol. 62, no. 12, pp. 3261–3271, 2014.
- [2] V. Rizzello, M. Nerini, M. Joham, B. Clerckx, and W. Utschick, “User-driven adaptive CSI feedback with ordered vector quantization,” *IEEE Wireless Commun. Lett.*, vol. 12, no. 11, pp. 1956–1960, 2023.
- [3] C. Wen, W. Shih, and S. Jin, “Deep learning for massive MIMO CSI feedback,” *IEEE Wireless Commun. Lett.*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 748–751, Mar. 2018.
- [4] J. Guo, C.-K. Wen, S. Jin, and G. Y. Li, “Convolutional neural network-based multiple-rate compressive sensing for massive MIMO CSI feedback: Design, simulation, and analysis,” *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 2827–2840, 2020.
- [5] Z. Hu, G. Liu, Q. Xie, J. Xue, D. Meng, and D. Gündüz, “A learnable optimization and regularization approach to massive MIMO CSI feedback,” *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 104–116, 2024.
- [6] H. Wu, M. Zhang, Y. Shao, K. Mikolajczyk, and D. Gündüz, “MIMO channel as a neural function: Implicit neural representations for extreme CSI compression in massive MIMO systems,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2403.13615>
- [7] M. B. Mashhadi, Q. Yang, and D. Gündüz, “Distributed deep convolutional compression for massive MIMO CSI feedback,” *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 2621–2633, 2021.
- [8] M. Sattari, D. Gündüz, and T. Svensson, “Dynamic model fine-tuning for extreme MIMO CSI compression,” 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.18250>
- [9] J. Zeng, J. Sun, G. Gui, B. Adebisi, T. Ohtsuki, H. Gacanin, and H. Sari, “Downlink CSI feedback algorithm with deep transfer learning for FDD massive MIMO systems,” *IEEE Trans. Cogn. Commun. Netw.*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1253–1265, 2021.
- [10] Z. Liu, L. Wang, L. Xu, and Z. Ding, “Deep learning for efficient CSI feedback in massive MIMO: Adapting to new environments and small datasets,” *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, pp. 1–1, 2024.
- [11] X. Li, J. Guo, C.-K. Wen, S. Jin, S. Han, and X. Wang, “Multi-task learning-based CSI feedback design in multiple scenarios,” *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 71, no. 12, pp. 7039–7055, 2023.
- [12] J. Ballé, D. Minnen, S. Singh, S. J. Hwang, and N. Johnston, “Variational image compression with a scale hyperprior,” in *Int. Conf. Learn. Represent. (ICLR)*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=rkcQFMZRB>
- [13] A. Alkhateeb, “DeepMIMO: A generic deep learning dataset for millimeter wave and massive MIMO applications,” in *Proc. Inf. Theory Appl. Workshop (ITA)*, San Diego, CA, Feb 2019, pp. 1–8.
- [14] T. van Rozendaal, I. A. Huijben, and T. Cohen, “Overfitting for fun and profit: Instance-adaptive data compression,” in *Int. Conf. Learn. Represent. (ICLR)*, 2021. [Online]. Available: https://openreview.net/forum?id=oFp8Mx_V5FL
- [15] S. Jaeckel, L. Raschkowski, K. Börner, and L. Thiele, “Quadriga: A 3-d multi-cell channel model with time evolution for enabling virtual field trials,” *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 62, no. 6, pp. 3242–3256, 2014.